

Wind-Power Development: A Critical Analysis of Sustainable Energy System for Educational Community

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigates the potential of harnessing wind resource for generation of electricity in a University community to improve power supply for research purposes and technological innovations. The research method and materials include wind data mining, design and development of prototype wind-power system to harness wind resource for improved power system. Wind velocities at different times and various heights in the study area were captured using anemometer. Statistical technique was deployed during this study for critical analysis. Results show that useful electricity can be generated from wind resource within the University community. The study outcomes, further show that wind-power generation improves with increase in height of the wind turbine system. Findings indicate that on Day 1, wind velocities of 1.2m/s in the morning and 3.8m/s in the afternoon were obtained at the height of 2m. Whereas, at the height of 10m, the wind velocities of 3.0m/s in the morning and 4.0m/s in the afternoon were obtained. Natural vegetations, tall buildings and some economic trees affect smooth flow of air and reduces the wind velocity especially at the lower turbine height. Based on the findings, a wind turbine system should be sited in areas that are free from natural vegetation and encumbrances. A minimum wind turbine height of 10m is however, proposed for improved wind-power generation in the study area. In general, wind velocity, height and area of the turbine rotor blade play significant role in the power generation performance.

Keywords: Power, renewable energy, turbine, velocity and wind.

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INTRODUCTION

Electricity plays significant role at homes, offices, government institutions, private organizations, industries and universities to mention but just a few. It is an indispensable energy source for

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economic growth and development. Reliable power supply enhance productivity and facilitates delivery of core university responsibilities including effective learning, research, educational development and business development. Energy poverty limits productivity and economic growth. In Nigeria, unreliable power system undermines investors' confidence [1-2], many industries have shut down production and operations while some are struggling to break even because of unavailability of sustainable energy system [3]. This study assesses the potential of wind renewable energy system using sustainable design for improved power supply in Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU) community. Renewable energy resources play significant role in the future of clean electrical energy generation due to the increasing concerns on global warming and air pollution generated from the activities of conventional electrical generation processes.

Renewable energy resources include hybrid biogas, solar, wind and pumped-hydro off grid system [4-7]. This study focuses on renewable wind-power development. Recent studies show that wind energy is one of the important forms of renewable energy resources in the world [8-10]. Evidently, wind resource is effective and friendly to the environment. Wind resource plays significant role in electricity generation in many countries. In the last two decades, attention have been shifted towards the development of wind turbine system. To determine the wind speed frequency, Weibull function is suitable as discussed in [11-14]. A wind turbine generator produces electricity by converting mechanical energy into electrical energy. The amount electrical energy produced is proportional to the amount of mechanical energy being used to spin the rotor blades and the size of the coil winding [15-19]. The greater the electrical demand placed on the generator; the more mechanical force is required to turn the rotor. Wind resource is used to generate electricity that is either stored using battery [20-21] or supply directly to laboratories and offices to power essential research tools including computers and broadband systems [22-24]. Wind turbine converts kinetic energy from mechanical energy into electrical energy. Renewable energy has a direct relationship with sustainable development through its impact on human development and economic productivity. Renewable energy resources provide opportunities in energy security, social and economic development, energy access, climate change mitigation and reduction of environmental and health impacts. Fig 1, shows typical hybrid renewable energy system consisting wind turbine, solar, biogas and pumped-hydro system.

Figure 1. Hybrid Renewable Energy System
Source: [4]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Renewable energy plays significant role by reducing greenhouse emissions compared to coal and natural gas in electricity generation. It has been estimated that wind power could supply 7% to 34% of global electricity needs by 2050 [25]. However, wind power faces a large number of technical, economic, financial and other barriers. Climate change mitigation initiatives resulting in CO₂-

emission reduction have played a significant role in promoting wind power development. Innovative hybrid systems have emerged between countries and regions. The emergence of wind as an important source of world energy demand has taken surprising dimensions. Wind is available everywhere in the world, in some places with considerable energy density. Wind energy harnesses kinetic energy from moving air. The primary application of wind energy to climate change mitigation is to produce electricity from large turbines located onshore and offshore.

Wind velocity, is a fundamental atmospheric quantity caused by air movement, usually due to changes in temperature. Wind velocity is commonly measured with an anemometer [26]. It is important to investigate the wind velocity of a particular area before developing a wind turbine system for electricity generation. The need for harnessing energy from wind is becoming a high demand because it is green and environmentally friendly. Various methods for evaluation and determination of wind characteristics have been discussed in the literature [27-30]. However, wind data across the country have been reported [31-32]. The methods for analyzing wind resource data include normal and Lognormal, Rayleigh, Weibull and Gumbel probability distributions among others are presented [33]. Similarly, analysis of wind speed using the daily wind data obtained from Nigeria Meteorological Agency, Oshodi, Lagos, employed Weibull, Lognormal and Normal probability density function [34]. Weibull distribution has been reported suitable for analysis of measured wind data including interpretation and prediction of the characteristics of wind profile.

Although wind power generation systems have evolved considerably in design and development, however, faces some technical and environmental challenges due to the dynamic characteristic of wind, as it varies in locations and heights. The efficiency of a wind system is affected by these factors [35]. Thus, prior to design and deployment of wind turbine system, it is important to investigate the wind characteristics of such environment. Wind turbine systems usually consist of three-blade horizontal axis, to take advantage of the variation of wind velocity. Other method for wind turbine development include vertical rotor design. Mathematical model for evaluation of wind turbine potential is discussed [36]. In this study, the line graph and mean value of wind velocity are used in the evaluation of wind-power potential in the study area. Wind velocity in a particular location helps in the design process of the wind-power system for efficient power generation.

Turbine systems are used to generate electricity from wind velocity. There are horizontal-axis wind turbine (HAWT) and vertical-axis wind turbine (VAWT) [37].

Figure 2. Wind Turbine System

Anemometers are commonly used in measuring wind velocity as applied in this research. The air flow turns the shaft at a rate roughly proportional to the wind velocity. Therefore, counting the shaft's revolutions over a set time interval produce a value proportional to the average wind velocity for a wide range of speeds. The speed of anemometer rotation is proportional to the wind velocity because

the force produced on an object is proportional to the velocity of the gas or fluid flowing through it. However, in practice, other factors influence the rotational speed, which includes turbulence produced by the apparatus, increasing drag in opposition to the torque produced by the cups/fan and support arms, and friction on the mount point.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The wind-power potential is assessed in terms of the wind velocity at different heights interval within the community. The values of wind velocity obtained using anemometer at different time intervals and heights for seven days are tabulated. The results obtained reflects unique potential quantity and a useful wind resource that can be harnessed for development of wind-power system for AKSU community. Fig. 3, represents typical anemometer for wind velocity measurement. Fig 4 shows wind data acquisition process at different heights.

Figure 3. Hand-Held Anemometer

Figure 4 Wind Data Acquisition

Wind Power Analysis

Figure 5. Wind Power Analysis

$$\text{Kinetic Energy (K.E)} = \frac{1}{2} mv^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Power (P)} = \frac{K.E}{t} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \times mv^2}{t} = \frac{1}{2} \times v^2 \times \frac{m}{t} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{As Mass flow rate} = \frac{m}{t} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Distance (L)} = \text{Velocity} \times \text{Time} = vt \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Time (t)} = \frac{L}{v} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Density } (\rho) = \frac{\text{mass}}{\text{volume}} = \frac{m}{v} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Mass} = \text{density} \times \text{volume} = \rho \times v = \rho \times A \times L \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Power (P)} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \times v^2 \times \rho \times A \times L}{\left(\frac{L}{v}\right)} = \frac{1}{2} \times v^2 \times \rho \times A \times v \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Power (P)} = \frac{1}{2} \times A \times \rho \times v^3 \quad (9)$$

Where ρ = density of the air in $\text{kg/m}^3 = 1.223 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $A = \pi r^2$; area of the circle swept by the rotor blades (m^2) and V = wind velocity (m/s). Thus, the wind-power generation is significantly based on the density of the air, the swept area of the wind turbine blades and wind velocity in the area. In this circumstance, wind velocity is the most significant input variable because it is cubed, whereas the other input variables are also important but not as wind velocity.

In this study, a prototype wind-power system was developed locally, using the available materials including blade HAWT system, gearbox, DC generator, inverter and battery. The battery stores energy generated. The prototype was developed to evaluate potential of wind-power system in the study area. Fig 6, presents prototype model system.

Figure 6. Block Diagram of the Model System

In the model system, the blades spin, a shaft drives an electrical generator to produce electricity. The gearbox improves slow rotational speed of the rotor to a high-speed motor for improved power generation. A modified sine wave inverter was used, it takes 12V, DC input and processed out 220V, AC output to power AC appliances was used in this study. Fig 7 shows the continuity test of the wind turbine generator coil.

Figure 7. Continuity Test of the Wind Turbine Generator Coil

Figure 8. Inverter AC Output

Some fundamental tests such as continuity test of the generator coil and inverter output voltage were carried out to ensure functionality of the developed prototype.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of wind velocity obtained at different heights ranging from 2m to 12m at different time intervals. The experimental analysis shows that there is variation of wind velocity at different height within AKSU community in the morning and afternoon as observed in Fig 9-Fig.15. From Fig 9, result show that wind velocity per height favors primarily 10m and 12m heights respectively. Lower turbine heights are not favored in this analysis because of encumbrances (buildings, tall natural vegetations) around the studied area.

Figure 9. Comparison of Day 1 Wind Velocities against Height

From Fig. 9, a distinctive indication between the morning and afternoon results with respect to different wind turbine heights are highlighted. A clear disparity between the two (A1 and M1) times of analysis and their effect on the wind turbine choice of height design. This result point to the fact a careful study should be employed before siting a wind turbine for energy generation. Furthermore, power generation can be achieved in the afternoon than morning, as depicted in Fig 9.

Figure 10. Comparison of Day 2 Wind Velocities against Height

Fig 10 depicts a comparative analysis (M2 and A2). From this presentation, in A2 (afternoon) time of study was mostly favored, morning session was not as favorable and informative for suitable design.

Figure 11. Comparison of Day 3 Wind Velocities against Height

M3 and A3 results show a stable wind velocity between 2m – 8m turbine heights respectively. However, between the turbine heights of 10m – 12m, there was a slight wind velocity variation at A3 but M3 in this case remain constant, as shown in Fig 11.

Fig 12: Comparison of Day 4 wind velocities against height

From Fig. 12, M4 (morning) and A4 (afternoon), test results demonstrate a more suitable wind flow in the morning, windy day. The afternoon results were not favorable in comparative terms. In any case, both results favor (10m - 12m) heights of wind turbine design.

Figure 13. Comparison of Day 5 Wind Velocities against Height

In Fig. 13, the results are presented. The research analysis shows a fluctuation of wind velocity in the afternoon followed with a stable flow between (10m - 12m) wind turbine heights. Morning session analysis presented, further buttresses a strong correlation between the wind turbine height and velocity in this study.

Figure 14. Comparison of Day 6 Wind Velocities against Height

For the results in M6 and A6, there are slight variation between the morning and afternoon period during this analysis at 2m of the turbine height. Observably, the wind velocity was relatively low at 2m in the morning. It is also noted that at 4m and above, the wind velocity improves significantly in comparison with the afternoon wind velocity, as shown in Fig 14. This result shows that the morning weather characterization was windy, which probably increase the wind velocity during the analysis.

Figure 15. Comparison of Day 6 Wind Velocities against Height

Fig 15, presents M7 and A7 results which indicate a variation in the morning and afternoon statistics at 2m of the wind turbine height. Also, at 4m of the turbine height, a corresponding result is achieved in both cases.

Figure 16. Comparison of Day 6 Wind Velocities against Height

In Fig.16, curves show that wind turbine heights of 2m between the morning and afternoon periods of test are almost the similar. This is because other available results between 4m – 8m are almost constant except with a slight variation between 8m - 10m. It is also noted that the results between 10 – 12m remain almost the same. The finding clearly points to the fact a more suitable design of wind turbine infrastructure rests on the height of the turbine to avoid building and vegetation obstructions for effective power generation.

DISCUSSION

The wind-power system is modeled using the overall average wind velocity and turbine height obtained in the study area.

Table 1. Average wind velocity (m/s) and Height (m)

S/N	Average Wind Velocity (m/s)	Height (m)
1	3.54	2
2	3.91	4
3	3.94	6
4	4.17	8
5	4.49	10
6	4.54	12
6	4.54	12

From Table 1, a comparative analysis of the overall average velocity against height are presented. Hence, a correlation between the tested parameters give a strong indication that the higher the height of the wind turbines, the better the results and the service delivery (energy generation) in this scenario. There is improvement in the afternoon wind velocity compared to the morning wind velocity. The results show availability of average wind velocity of 4.52 m/s in the region of 10m – 12m turbine height within AKSU community main campus. Wind velocity increases with increase in the height of the wind turbine system.

Power availability (P_{avail}), in AKSU community main campus is calculated using the given equation;

$$P_{avail} = \frac{1}{2} \times \rho \times A \times V^3 \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the wind density and A is the sweep area of the blade. Thus using radius of the rotor blade of the wind turbine as 1.0m, wind density given as (ρ) = 1.23 kg/m³. The sweep area of the blade

$$A = \pi r^2 = 3.142 \times 1 \times 1 = 3.142m^2 \quad (11)$$

Therefore, using the data obtained from the study, in equation 10, the values obtained from mathematical analysis for power available in the wind at 2m height, 3.54 m/s velocity is;

$$P_{avail} = \frac{1}{2} \times \rho \times A \times V^3 = 85.72 W \quad (12)$$

The potential power that can be harnessed from wind in a second using a typical wind turbine system with the given characteristic in AKSU community is calculated using eqn (10). Fig 17, presents the potential power in wind within the research location in seconds using the given height intervals.

Figure 17. Average Wind Velocity and Power Potential

It is observed that at the height 2m, 84.70W was available and at 4m height, 115.50W was available respectively. It is also noted that the height of 12m, 180.80W was available. Thus, the higher the height (m) of the turbine system the higher the power (W) availability.

DEVELOPMENT OF PROTOTYPE WIND-POWER SYSTEM

The prototype wind-power system was developed using available materials, gearbox system, motor, shaft, blade, inverter. During the study, the turbine blades were exposed to wind, initiating the rotor's rotation and subsequent generation of power. The results were taken by measuring the voltage (V) output, current (A) output and power (W) output generated from the prototype wind-power system was computed using:

$$P = IV, \tag{13}$$

where P represents power (W), I is the current (A) and voltage (V). Fig 18 presents the power generation per hour from 8am to 9pm for Day I.

Figure 18. Wind Turbine Power (W) Output vs Time (Hour) for Day I

From Fig 18, peak power output, 12.9W, was observed around 11:00am followed by 7.44W by 2:00pm. In average, more power was generated between the hours of 8:00am and 2:00pm compare to the evening section of 3:00pm - 9:00pm. It is also noted that more wind velocity which drives the fan blades to produce more torque on the rotor shaft, increase in the revolution per minute (r.p.m) and more output voltage from the generator. It has been noted that the wind-power system is cost effective as it does not require fuel for operations, rather a low-cost maintenance practice procedure[38][39][40] of lubricating the rotational sections including the shaft and gear systems of the wind turbine system [41] for performance enhancement. Fig 19 shows power generation per hour from 8am - 9pm for Day II.

Figure 19. Wind Power (W) Output vs Time (Hour) for Day II

Fig 19 presents Day II wind-power analysis using the prototype model, it was observed that the peak power output of 12.91W occurred around 9.00am. Thereafter, degenerated to about 4.76W by 10am and staggered to 7.26W around 3pm. Note that there was a deep power degeneration of 3.06W around 4pm and later rise to 7.44W around 7pm. The fluctuation in the power generation as observed in Fig 19 is due to the variation of wind velocity around the study area.

CONCLUSION

A critical assessment of wind-power availability in AKSU community has been presented. It has been observed that wind-power improves with increase in height of the wind turbine system. Natural vegetation and tall trees affect smooth flow of air and reduces the wind velocity especially at the lower turbine height. Based on the findings, a minimum wind turbine height of 10m is recommended for improved wind-power generation in the study area. However, it has also been deduced that the design of blade and gear systems of the wind turbine can also improve the overall efficiency of the wind-power generation. Further observation from Fig 18 and Fig 19, show that wind-power electricity generation fluctuates due to dynamic characteristics of wind velocity, thus an improved wind-power system should incorporate battery storage and compensation system in the design to maintain adequate power supply to appliances during the deep power degeneration periods. In conclusion, wind-power system is cost effective as it does not require fuel for operations, rather a low-cost maintenance practice procedure of lubrication on the shaft and gear systems for optimum performance is desired for sustainability.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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